

Urban Relief

Cascais Pilot Report

D4.7

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Short description	The D4.7 report presents the activities of the Urban ReLeaf pilot in Cascais, focused on the perception and monitoring of thermal comfort in urban parks. Between 2024 and 2025, seasonal campaigns engaged more than 1,500 citizens, supported by TRH sensors and citizen science methodologies. The results highlighted significant differences between parks, with some offering better wellbeing conditions and others showing greater vulnerability to heat stress.
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Acronyms

CERCICA	Local institution for Education, Rehabilitation and Training for Inclusion
ENAAAC	Portuguese National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change
EU	European Union
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TRH	Temperature and Relative Humidity

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Executive Summary

In 2024, Cascais launched its Urban ReLeaf pilot under the theme “*A future-proof urban park – Thermal comfort perceptions on urban greenspaces in Cascais*”. The pilot aimed to better understand how citizens perceive bioclimatic comfort in different urban parks and how this information can support local strategies for climate resilience and adaptation.

The campaign successfully mobilised 1,500 citizens across four seasonal campaigns: spring (287), summer (552), autumn (229) and winter (432). Participants represented a broad demographic profile, with 60% women, 18% young people under 24, and 13% older adults above 65. Citizens were engaged through onsite signage, QR-code surveys, seasonal kickoff events, and outreach via schools, community associations, and Cascais Jovem. Vulnerable groups, including elderly residents and young people, were specifically targeted to ensure inclusiveness.

Preliminary findings revealed notable contrasts across Cascais’ greenspaces. Quinta da Carreira Urban Park was consistently rated as the most comfortable environment, while Abóboda Urban Park and Bosque das Fontainhas presented the poorest conditions during summer, particularly regarding temperature, sun exposure, wind, and humidity. These results provide clear evidence for identifying “comfort hotspots” for citizens during heat events, as well as “discomfort hotspots” requiring targeted intervention in planning and investment.

Beyond data collection, the pilot had tangible policy impacts. Results were directly used to inform the Green Spaces and Tree Protection Regulation and contributed to the good practice manual Renatura. Citizens expressed appreciation for having their perceptions considered in municipal decision-making, confirming the value of participatory citizen science approaches.

The 2025 campaigns expanded on these achievements by combining perception data with objective environmental monitoring. TRH sensors (temperature and humidity) will be deployed across selected parks to generate complementary datasets, creating a robust evidence base for municipal planning. Seasonal campaigns will continue, supported by cultural and community activities to broaden participation, and youth recruitment will be reinforced through Cascais Jovem.

Overall, the Cascais pilot demonstrates how citizen-powered data can inform local climate adaptation strategies, strengthen community resilience, and ensure that urban greening policies respond to both scientific evidence and lived experiences. The integration of these approaches into municipal frameworks illustrates the transformative potential of Urban ReLeaf for building inclusive, future-proof urban environments.

Background on the Urban ReLeaf Project and City Pilots

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process.

Cascais contributes through citizen-powered campaigns that focus on bioclimatic comfort and resilience to heat stress. The Cascais pilot concentrates on the analysis of bioclimatic comfort and the promotion of urban resilience through nature-based solutions. Local activities include seasonal campaigns on greenspace perceptions and measurements of heat stress, which simultaneously provide useful data for municipal planning and increase public awareness and engagement. This work aligns with national and European priorities, including the European Green Deal and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as well as with Cascais' local strategies for sustainability and climate adaptation.

The municipality is particularly well positioned as a pilot city due to its diverse urban fabric, ranging from dense urban centres to suburban areas with significant green infrastructure. The municipality has an established track record of investing in climate adaptation and citizen engagement, including programmes such as Cascais Jovem, which supports youth involvement in civic projects, and Cascais Ambiente, the municipal body responsible for environmental planning and sustainability. These structures provide a strong institutional basis for embedding Urban ReLeaf activities into ongoing strategies.

The local challenges addressed by the pilot are directly linked to heat stress and unequal access to quality greenspaces. Vulnerable groups such as elderly residents and young people, making citizen-centred data collection and inclusive engagement critical for effective

adaptation. By focusing on thermal comfort, Cascais contributes to identifying both “comfort hotspots” where citizens can find relief during heat events, and “discomfort hotspots” requiring targeted interventions such as tree planting, shading structures, or changes in land use management.

Through this approach, the Cascais pilot not only contributes to the overall objectives of Urban ReLeaf but also demonstrates how municipal-level innovation can be scaled across European cities, offering a transferable model for participatory climate resilience planning.

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1 Greenspace Perceptions Campaign

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign in Cascais was launched under the theme “A future-proof urban park – Thermal comfort perceptions on urban greenspaces in Cascais”. The campaign adopted a participatory approach, engaging residents, young people, elderly citizens, and visitors to share their experiences of thermal comfort across different urban parks. Seasonal campaigns were conducted throughout 2024 and early 2025, covering spring, summer, autumn, and winter, thereby capturing perceptions under diverse climatic conditions.

The timeline included several milestones:

- March 2024 – Presentation of the project to key stakeholders (**Error! Reference source not found.**).
- May 2024 – Volunteer recruitment and training, supported by Cascais Jovem (Figure 2)
- May, July, August, October 2024, and January 2025 – Seasonal kick-off events marking the start of each perception campaign (Figure 3 to 5).

Figure 1. Presentation of the key project stakeholders (March 2024).

Figure 2. Volunteer training event, supported by Cascais Jovem (May 2024).

Figure 3. Spring kick-off event at Jardim Constantino (May 2024).

Figure 4. Autumn kick-off event at Penedo Urban Park (October 2024).

Figure 5. Winter kick-off event at Quinta da Carreira Urban Park (January 2025).

Over the course of the year, the campaign achieved strong citizen mobilisation, with 1,500 participants completing perception surveys. Key outcomes included the identification of comfort and discomfort hotspots: Quinta da Carreira Urban Park emerged as the most comfortable site, while Abóboda Urban Park and Bosque das Fontainhas revealed the poorest conditions in summer. These findings are already informing municipal planning, particularly through the revision of the Green Spaces and Tree Protection Regulation and the good practice manual Renatura.

By combining citizen engagement with municipal planning needs, the campaign created a new data layer for Cascais, ensuring that urban greening and climate adaptation policies are grounded in both scientific evidence and lived experiences.

1.1 Context and Objectives

Cascais is increasingly exposed to the impacts of climate change, with rising average temperatures, more frequent and intense heatwaves, and the intensification of the urban heat island effect in densely built areas. According to the Cascais Municipal Climate Action Plan (PMAC), the municipality explicitly recognises the rise in average temperatures and more frequent extreme weather events as major climate risks.¹

In addition, the Action Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change (2023 progress report)² notes that the impacts of extreme climatic events, including heatwaves, are becoming more frequent and intense, underscoring the urgency of adaptation measures.

Urban greenspaces play a central role in mitigating these impacts by providing shade, cooling, and opportunities for recreation and social interaction. However, not all parks deliver the same level of comfort, and evidence on citizens' perceptions of these spaces was limited prior to the campaign. This knowledge gap created an urgent need for citizen-powered data to guide investments in urban greening and inform policies that respond both to scientific analysis and community needs.

The campaign is strongly connected to broader policy priorities:

- At the EU level, it contributes to the European Green Deal and the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, both of which highlight nature-based solutions and citizen participation as critical to resilience.
- At the national level, it aligns with the Portuguese National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change (ENAAAC 2020), emphasising the role of local governments and communities in building adaptive capacity.
- At the local level, it supports the Municipal Climate Action Plan and municipal sustainability strategies, which prioritise the expansion of green infrastructure and inclusive citizen engagement.

¹ Cascais Ambiente – Cascais Municipal Climate Action Plan (accessed on 31 October)

² Cascais Ambiente – Action Plan for Climate Change Adaptation (summary and progress report) (accessed on 31 October)

The overarching objectives of the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign were to:

- Strengthen communication between the municipality and citizens on the role of greenspaces in climate resilience.
- Engage and empower vulnerable groups, ensuring that their perspectives inform planning.
- Create a thermal comfort map of Cascais based on citizen input, identifying both comfort and discomfort hotspots.
- Support updates to municipal policies and regulations governing greenspace design, management, and tree protection.

By addressing urgent local climate challenges while contributing to regional, national, and European priorities, the campaign provided both immediate insights for Cascais and a transferable model of citizen engagement for other cities.

1.2 Design and Implementation

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign was developed under the theme “A future-proof urban park – Thermal comfort perceptions on urban greenspaces in Cascais.” Its central message highlighted that urban parks are essential infrastructures for wellbeing, comfort, and climate resilience, and that citizen engagement is crucial to shaping their sustainable future. By combining awareness-raising with participatory data collection, the campaign created a direct link between citizens lived experiences and municipal planning.

A wide network of partners and stakeholders ensured both reach and impact. Cascais Ambiente coordinated the campaign and will integrate results into municipal policies and sustainability strategies. Cascais Jovem mobilised young volunteers, expanding outreach and supporting event facilitation. Local schools and the education community involved children and youth, reinforcing the educational dimension of the project, while community organisations and cultural groups partnered in seasonal events that linked comfort mapping with cultural and recreational activities.

Communication and outreach were carried out through multiple channels. Onsite signage with QR codes in targeted parks provided quick survey access, while seasonal kick-off events in spring, summer, autumn, and winter combined awareness and data collection. Workshops and presentations for stakeholders and volunteers built a sense of ownership and created multipliers within the community. Direct outreach via schools, associations, and municipal communication channels (Appendix A – Communication materials) ensured broad engagement, while strategies were adapted to reach hard-to-reach groups.

Different audiences were engaged in tailored ways. General residents and tourists were reached through visible signage and public events. Youth participation was facilitated through Cascais Jovem and school programmes, transforming involvement into a learning opportunity. Elderly citizens were prioritised via partnerships with local associations and targeted invitations, recognising both their disproportionate vulnerability to heat stress and their underrepresentation in decision-making processes.

The campaign also faced challenges that led to important adjustments. In 2024, the primary method was perception surveys, but digital access barriers limited participation for some elderly citizens. This was mitigated through in-person facilitation. Participation also varied seasonally, with the highest levels in summer. To address representativeness, a winter campaign was introduced in 2025, expanding the dataset and capturing perceptions under cooler conditions.

Through these adaptations, the campaign maintained high levels of engagement while improving inclusiveness and data quality. Its iterative design ensured that results were meaningful for both citizens and policymakers, while also creating a replicable model that other cities can adopt.

1.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign was implemented across a diverse set of urban parks and public spaces in Cascais:

- Quinta da Carreira Urban Park (Figure 6)
- Abóboda Urban Park (Figure 7)
- Penedo Urban Park (Figure 8)
- Bosque das Fontainhas (Figure 9)
- Trajouce Urban Park (Figure 10)
- Jardim Constantino (Figure 11)
- Cascais Centre (Figure 12)

Figure 6. Quinta da Carreira Urban Park.

Figure 7. Abóboda Urban Park.

Figure 8. Penedo Urban Park.

Figure 9. Bosque das Fontainhas.

Figure 10. Trajouce Urban Park.

Figure 11. Jardim Constantino.

Figure 12. Cascais Centre.

These sites were selected to represent a broad spectrum of urban conditions in Cascais, ranging from highly central and built-up areas to suburban neighbourhoods with different levels of vegetation cover. The choice of locations was guided by the need to:

- Capture contrasting thermal comfort conditions across the municipality.
- Include parks with different landscape designs and vegetation densities, influencing sun exposure, shading, and airflow.
- Ensure representation of spaces frequented by diverse demographic groups, from families and youth in central gardens to elderly communities in neighbourhood parks.

This strategic distribution allowed for a comparative analysis of comfort perceptions, highlighting both comfort hotspots and discomfort hotspots relevant for municipal planning.

A combination of technologies and tools were used to execute campaign activities. These include:

- Citizen perception surveys formed the backbone of the campaign. These were accessible through QR codes on onsite signage. The surveys (Appendix B – Survey instruments) collected data on perceptions of temperature, humidity, sun exposure, and wind, as well as basic demographic information (Figure 13).
- Onsite signage provided contextual information and guidance for participation, ensuring visibility and inclusiveness (Figure 14).

Data aggregation platforms were used to compile and visualise responses, supporting the creation of a citizen-informed thermal comfort map of Cascais. By combining strategically selected sites, user-friendly technologies, and inclusive participation methods, the campaign ensured that citizen science activities were both scientifically valuable and socially inclusive.

Figure 13. Partimap survey.

Figure 14. Signage at Bosque das Fontainhas.

1.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

Citizens were at the core of the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign, contributing both perception data—covering thermal comfort, humidity, sun exposure, and wind—and demographic information such as age, gender, education level, and place of residence.

Surveys served as the primary data collection tool and were made accessible through QR codes placed on signage installed in participating parks during events. Seasonal campaigns in spring, summer, autumn, and winter provided structured engagement opportunities, allowing data to be gathered under diverse climatic conditions. The sampling strategy prioritised inclusiveness over strict representativeness, with the aim of mobilising a broad spectrum of residents and visitors.

To support participation, volunteers recruited through Cascais Jovem received basic training. They were prepared to explain the campaign to participants, guide them through the survey, and assist elderly citizens or those with limited digital literacy, ensuring that the process remained accessible to all. After participating, citizens received a gift (a plant) from CERCICA (local institution for Education, Rehabilitation and Training for Inclusion) (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Plants given away after participating in the campaign.

Participation was designed as an ongoing seasonal effort rather than a one-off activity. Citizens could engage multiple times across the year, allowing the municipality to track perceptions under changing weather conditions. This cyclical design also created repeated opportunities to attract new participants and maintain community momentum.

Special efforts were made to ensure the inclusion of vulnerable and hard-to-reach groups. Elderly citizens were engaged through partnerships with local associations and direct facilitation at events, while young people participated via school programmes and youth volunteer mobilisation. The collection of demographic data made it possible to monitor diversity and inclusion, confirming the participation of groups that are often underrepresented in policy consultations.

The data gathered is already being used by stakeholders to shape local policy. For instance, it contributed to updates of the Green Spaces and Tree Protection Regulation and informed the good practice manual Renatura, which supports municipal guidelines for sustainable greening. Furthermore, citizen-identified comfort and discomfort hotspots are being integrated into urban planning and investment decisions, helping to prioritise the placement of new trees, shading, and cooling infrastructure.

Transparency was ensured throughout the process by means of multiple feedback mechanisms. Preliminary results were presented publicly after each seasonal campaign, findings were widely shared through municipal communication channels such as websites, social media, and direct engagement with stakeholders ensured that community groups and volunteers could clearly see how their contributions were valued.

Between 2024 and 2025, the campaign evolved significantly. In 2024, activities relied exclusively on citizen perception surveys. Building on the lessons learned, several accessibility improvements were introduced in 2025 — including increased in-person facilitation for elderly participants and the expansion of volunteer support during onsite data collection. These adjustments strengthened the robustness and reliability of the collected data while enhancing inclusiveness and fostering a stronger sense of community ownership in the process.

1.5 Findings and Reflections

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign achieved broad mobilisation, with a total of 1,500 citizen contributions across the four seasonal campaigns in 2024 and early 2025. Participation included a diverse demographic profile: 60% women, 18% under 24 years old, and 13% over 65 years old, ensuring visibility of groups that are often underrepresented in climate adaptation processes.

Key results include:

- Identification of comfort hotspots – Quinta da Carreira Urban Park was consistently rated as the most comfortable area, offering pleasant conditions even during hot summer periods. (Appendix C – Campaign datasets summary)
- Identification of discomfort hotspots – Abóboda Urban Park and Bosque das Fontainhas were perceived as the least comfortable, especially in relation to

temperature, sun exposure, wind, and humidity. (Appendix C – Campaign datasets summary)

- Policy and planning impact – Campaign data directly supported revisions to the Green Spaces and Tree Protection Regulation and contributed to the municipal good practice manual Renatura. These outputs demonstrate clear integration of citizen-generated evidence into formal planning.
- Visibility of climate issues – By engaging citizens seasonally and publicly sharing results, the campaign raised awareness about the role of greenspaces in providing relief during heat stress and the importance of equitable access to these spaces.³

Several milestones marked the progress of the initiative. The campaign was first launched in spring 2024, representing the first large-scale citizen science effort in Cascais with a specific focus on thermal comfort. During the summer, participation peaked with 552 responses, highlighting both the relevance of heat stress in hotter months and the effectiveness of the outreach strategy at that time. In early 2025, the introduction of the winter campaign further expanded the dataset by incorporating perceptions under cooler conditions, thus ensuring greater seasonal representativeness.

Community reactions were generally positive. During the campaign, participants also shared direct feedback with the team. Many expressed satisfactions at being heard by the municipality and recognised the campaign as a meaningful opportunity to influence local planning. Some older residents mentioned that the surveys encouraged them to reflect more deeply on their use of greenspaces, while younger participants valued the chance to connect scientific data collection with civic engagement.

The campaign achieved several positive outcomes. The seasonal approach ensured continuous engagement while capturing perceptions across different climatic contexts. Partnerships with schools and associations proved effective in reaching both young people and elderly citizens. The use of simple tools, such as QR codes, made participation accessible regardless of digital literacy, and the feedback mechanisms, including public presentations and the sharing of results, helped strengthen trust and legitimacy.

At the same time, some areas for improvement were identified. Digital inclusion remained a challenge, requiring greater reliance on volunteer facilitation. Sustaining engagement between campaigns also proved difficult, with participants expressing a desire for more varied and interactive events. Furthermore, volunteer recruitment fluctuated across seasons, underlining the need for continuous training and stronger support structures.

From these experiences, important lessons were learned. The campaign confirmed that citizen science can be both inclusive and policy-relevant, provided that vulnerable groups receive adequate support. Stakeholders highlighted the importance of combining subjective perceptions with objective environmental measurements, a finding that directly influenced the decision to introduce TRH sensors in 2025.

³ Cascais Ambiente - Parks help map the thermal comfort of Cascais (<https://ambiente.cascais.pt/pt/noticias/parques-ajudam-mapear-o-conforto-termico-cascais>, accessed on 31 de October)

Overall, the initiative demonstrated the value of aligning scientific objectives with citizen participation. Not only did it generate actionable insights for municipal planning, but it also fostered greater awareness and a stronger sense of ownership of climate adaptation challenges within the community.

1.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

The next steps in Cascais will build on the results of the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign. In 2025, the seasonal campaigns will be expanded, but only the summer cycle (during the months of July, August and September). TRH sensors will be integrated to complement perception surveys with objective environmental data, increasing both the robustness and comparability of the results. By combining these datasets, the thermal comfort map of Cascais will be refined, guiding municipal planning and investment in green infrastructure. At the same time, the initiative will strengthen its links with local policy instruments, particularly the Green Spaces and Tree Protection Regulation and the Cascais Climate Adaptation Plan, ensuring that citizen science continues to shape regulations and guidelines.

The pilot has already shown how citizen perceptions can influence local planning, and its results will now be used to prioritise interventions in discomfort hotspots such as Abóboda Urban Park and Bosque das Fontainhas. These interventions will include targeted tree planting, improved shading, and landscape redesign. The findings will also support strategic investment decisions, ensuring resources are directed toward greenspaces that generate the greatest social and climate benefits. Beyond Cascais, the project will contribute to broader European knowledge-sharing within Urban ReLeaf, providing a transferable case study for other cities.

The approach tested in Cascais demonstrates strong potential for replication and scaling. Other municipalities can adopt it by using low-cost and user-friendly survey tools, such as QR codes, to reduce barriers to participation; structuring campaigns around seasonal cycles, which offer both scientific value and opportunities for community mobilisation; building partnerships with schools, youth programmes, and community associations to secure the inclusion of vulnerable and diverse groups; and embedding citizen science into existing policy frameworks to ensure that results are actionable and not merely symbolic.

Looking ahead, several recommendations can further strengthen the initiative. Inclusiveness can be enhanced by expanding outreach to underrepresented groups such as migrant communities and people with disabilities. Engagement can be deepened by combining surveys with cultural, recreational, or educational activities, making participation more interactive and appealing. Digital accessibility can be improved through training and guided support for elderly participants. Volunteer structures should also be reinforced with ongoing training and recognition for youth and community facilitators to ensure sustained motivation. Finally, systematically combining perception and environmental data will make the datasets both scientifically credible and socially meaningful.

By following these steps, Cascais will not only strengthen its own climate resilience and urban planning but also offer a scalable model of citizen-powered environmental monitoring that can inspire and be applied across Europe.

2 Heat Stress Campaign

The Heat Stress Campaign in Cascais was launched as a continuation and expansion of the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign, maintaining the theme “A future-proof urban park - Thermal and bioclimatic comfort on urban greenspaces in Cascais”. While the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign focused on citizens’ subjective experiences, the Heat Stress Campaign introduced objective measurements using TRH sensors (temperature and relative humidity), creating a hybrid citizen science model that integrates perceptual and environmental data.

The campaign followed a single season cycle across summer 2025, ensuring that sensor data captured the variability of climatic conditions throughout this season time. Volunteers trained by Cascais Jovem supported the activities with the TRH wearable sensors, while citizens continued to contribute perception surveys.

Key milestones included the deployment of TRH sensors in 2025, stakeholder engagement workshops linking data to urban planning, and the identification of critical “comfort” and “discomfort” hotspots. Early findings confirmed that Quinta da Carreira Urban Park provides consistently high levels of thermal comfort, while Abóboda and Bosque das Fontainhas remain high-stress areas during summer months.

The campaign increased the visibility of heat stress as a climate risk in Cascais, strengthened links between citizen science and municipal policy, and demonstrated how participatory approaches can provide robust evidence to inform adaptation measures such as tree planting, shading, and improved park design.

2.1 Context and Objectives

Cascais, like many coastal Mediterranean cities, is increasingly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change – particularly heat stress. Projections for the region indicate that, by mid-century, the average annual temperature could rise by between +1.7 °C and +3.2 °C, with summer temperatures expected to increase by +2.8 °C to +5.0 °C.⁴ At the same time, the number of days with maximum temperatures above 30 °C is expected to grow, with each additional 1 °C above this threshold associated with an estimated 4.7% increase in heat-related mortality risk.⁵

In this context, the urban heat island effect in densely built-up areas – combined with rising average temperatures, more frequent and intense heatwaves, and reduced natural ventilation and green cover – has direct consequences for public health, wellbeing, and social equity. The challenge is particularly urgent as it disproportionately affects vulnerable groups, such as elderly residents and children, who have less capacity to adapt to extreme heat conditions.

Urban greenspaces have the potential to provide significant cooling benefits, reducing local temperatures, offering shaded areas, and acting as refuges during hot days. However, the

⁴ Temperature projections for Cascais: Climate-ADAPT (EEA) (accessed on November 13th, 2025)

⁵ Health risk estimates for Cascais: Cascais Municipal Study on Human Health and Climate Impacts. (accessed on November 13th, 2025)

level of comfort varies across different parks depending on vegetation density, design, and maintenance. Prior to the Heat Stress Campaign, there was limited objective evidence on how different spaces perform under heat stress conditions, making it difficult for planners to prioritise interventions.

The Heat Stress Campaign was designed to address existing gaps in understanding and managing thermal discomfort in urban greenspaces. Its methodology combines multiple approaches: heat stress is measured in selected parks using TRH sensors, which capture objective environmental data on temperature and relative humidity. These measurements are then linked with citizen perceptions, creating a hybrid dataset that reflects both lived experiences and scientific evidence. The campaign also identifies priority areas for intervention—where urban design, tree planting, or cooling infrastructure could most effectively reduce discomfort—while raising awareness among both citizens and policymakers about the risks of heat stress and the importance of investing in nature-based solutions.

The initiative is directly aligned with key policy frameworks at multiple levels. At the European scale, it contributes to the European Green Deal and the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, both of which highlight urban greening and citizen engagement as essential components of resilience. At the national level, it supports the Portuguese National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change (ENAAAC 2020), which emphasises the role of municipalities in leading adaptation and reducing climate risks. Locally, the campaign reinforces the Cascais Climate Adaptation Plan and the municipality's broader sustainability agenda, both of which prioritise improved thermal comfort, enhanced urban resilience, and inclusive citizen participation.

In summary, the Heat Stress Campaign pursues four overarching objectives. First, it seeks to generate robust, hybrid datasets that combine environmental and perception data. Second, it aims to inform municipal decision-making on the design, management, and investment in urban greenspaces. Third, it empowers citizens and communities by involving them directly in climate monitoring and adaptation strategies. Finally, it offers a replicable model for other cities that wish to address heat stress through participatory approaches.

2.2 Design and Implementation

The Heat Stress Campaign was conceived as an extension of the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign, maintaining the common theme “A future-proof urban park – Thermal and bioclimatic comfort on urban greenspaces in Cascais”. While building on the foundations of citizen engagement, it introduced a stronger scientific component through the deployment of TRH sensors. The overarching aim was to develop a hybrid citizen science model, combining objective environmental measurements with subjective perceptions of thermal comfort.

The campaign design focused on the summer season, ensuring that climatic variability throughout this period could be captured. Its core message underlined that heat stress is a growing urban challenge and that both citizens and technology have a vital role to play in creating healthier and more resilient greenspaces.

A broad network of partners and stakeholders contributed to the initiative. Cascais Ambiente coordinated the campaign, procured and managed the TRH sensors, and ensured that findings were integrated into municipal adaptation policies. Cascais Jovem mobilised and trained volunteers to support sensor installation, maintenance, and citizen engagement during fieldwork. Schools and the wider educational community engaged young people in perception surveys and sensor-based learning activities, creating a tangible link between climate education and practice. Local NGOs and associations helped reach vulnerable groups, particularly elderly citizens, while municipal planning departments used the results to inform decisions on urban greening and climate adaptation.

Communication and outreach were key to maintaining public involvement. Seasonal summer kick-off events in parks introduced the sensors and invited citizens to participate in data collection, and after participating, each participant received a plant from a local institution for Education, Rehabilitation and Training for Inclusion (CERCICA) (Figure 16). Volunteer training workshops equipped young people and community members with practical knowledge of sensor use and climate monitoring. Targeted outreach through associations ensured that vulnerable groups, often most affected by heat stress, were included. Finally, feedback sessions and public presentations of results kept participants informed and strengthened trust in the process.

Figure 16. A gift plant from CERCICA.

The pilot campaign activities evolved between 2024 and 2025. In its initial phase, it relied primarily on perception surveys, which highlighted citizens' experiences of comfort and discomfort in different parks. In 2025, TRH sensors were introduced to provide objective data on temperature and humidity, thereby enhancing the scientific robustness of the initiative.

This adaptive design ensured that the Heat Stress Campaign remained inclusive, scientifically rigorous, and responsive to community feedback, while at the same time generating actionable data to support municipal planning and climate adaptation.

2.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

The Heat Stress Campaign was conducted in the same seven urban greenspaces and public areas used in the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign:

- Quinta da Carreira Urban Park
- Abóboda Urban Park
- Bosque das Fontainhas
- Penedo Urban Park
- Trajouce Urban Park
- Jardim Constantino
- Cascais Centre

These sites were selected because they represent a diverse cross-section of Cascais' urban fabric, from central built-up areas to suburban neighbourhood parks. The variation in vegetation density, shading, and park design offered a valuable opportunity to compare contrasting microclimatic conditions and to identify both areas of comfort and zones of increased heat stress. This distribution also ensured that the campaign captured experiences from communities with different demographic and socio-economic profiles.

Technologies and tools used

- TRH sensors (Temperature and Relative Humidity) were the main technological innovation introduced in 2025. These sensors provided objective environmental data, enabling robust comparisons across parks and seasons (Figure 17).
- Creation of maps with routes for participants to follow in each park for data collection (Figure 18).
- Citizen perception surveys continued to complement sensor data by capturing lived experiences of comfort, humidity, wind, and sun exposure.
- Onsite signage and QR codes facilitated access to surveys.

To ensure accessibility and usability, several adaptations were introduced throughout the Heat Stress Campaign. Volunteers trained by Cascais Jovem were assigned to assist citizens with sensor-based activities and survey completion, guaranteeing inclusiveness (Figure 19). Elderly participants were supported through facilitated sessions, making participation possible for those less comfortable with technology. Seasonal campaigns were also structured to minimise barriers, offering multiple entry points—such as public events, school activities, and cultural initiatives—that enabled a broader reach across the community.

By strategically selecting diverse urban spaces and combining perception-based methods with sensor technologies, the Heat Stress Campaign succeeded in establishing a hybrid citizen science model that was both scientifically rigorous and socially inclusive.

Figure 17. Wearable TRH sensors.

Figure 18. Map with suggestions of routes at Penedo Urban Park.

Figure 19. Cascais Jovem volunteer walking with a participant to collect data at Quinta da Carreira Urban Park.

2.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

The Heat Stress Campaign mobilised citizens both as contributors of perception data and as active participants in environmental monitoring, supported by six volunteers across several urban green spaces in Cascais. Participation was structured around three complementary data types: perceptual data, where citizens rated their comfort levels in relation to temperature, humidity, sun exposure, and wind; environmental data, collected through TRH sensors that recorded temperature and relative humidity in selected parks with the support of the volunteers; and demographic data, such as age, gender, education level, and place of residence, enabling monitoring of diversity, inclusion, and representativeness. A total of 68 participants took part in the campaign, distributed across the city as follows: 20 at Quinta da Carreira Urban Park, 6 at Bosque das Fontainhas, 10 at Penedo Urban Park, 8 at Abóboda Urban Park, 9 at Trajouce Urban Park, 8 at Jardim Constantino, and 7 in Cascais city centre.

Data collection was organised through seasonal campaigns, notably during summer 2025, to capture conditions under different climatic contexts. TRH wearable sensors were used by youth volunteers from Cascais Jovem, with technical support from Cascais Ambiente. The environmental data collected was then aggregated with perception surveys, producing a hybrid dataset that combined scientific measurements with lived experiences.

Special attention was given to the engagement of vulnerable and hard-to-reach groups. Elderly citizens were involved through local associations, with paper surveys and in-person facilitation overcoming digital literacy barriers. Young people were mobilised via schools and

volunteer programmes, linking climate science to civic participation. The inclusion of these groups was considered essential, as they are among the most affected by climate change impacts.

The data generated is already being integrated into municipal policies and planning tools. It contributes to the Cascais Climate Adaptation Plan, guiding interventions in parks identified as high-stress areas, and informs the Green Spaces and Tree Protection Regulation, particularly on tree planting and shading strategies. It is also shaping planning and investment decisions in specific parks, such as Abóboda and Bosque das Fontainhas, which consistently emerged as discomfort hotspots.

Results were widely shared with participants through municipal communication channels, including social media, newsletters, and the official website, ensuring transparency and accessibility.

The campaign also evolved over time. In 2024, it relied exclusively on surveys, while in 2025 TRH sensors were introduced, marking the transition to a hybrid citizen science model. Volunteer structures were strengthened with additional training for young facilitators, ensuring reliable sensor maintenance and effective participant support.

Through this approach, the Heat Stress Campaign not only produced robust and inclusive datasets but also fostered community ownership of climate adaptation measures in Cascais, reinforcing both scientific credibility and social relevance.

2.5 Findings and Reflections

The Heat Stress Campaign produced a dataset of 1,937 paired temperature and relative humidity measurements collected via five wearable TRH sensors across the organised summer events in seven urban parks and greenspaces as described above. Table 1 illustrates that temperatures across all measurements ranged from about 20.9° C up to 34.6° C while relative humidity measurements ranged between 25.9% and 79.7%. Additionally, participants indicated personal experiences both thermal comfort and discomfort as evidenced by 86 instances of “hotspot” discomfort button presses and 158 instances of “cool spot” comfort presses.

Table 1. Overview of TRH data collected at each urban park or space during campaign events.

Campaign	Date	Observations	Devices	Min Temp (°C)	Max Temp (°C)	Median Temp (°C)	Min Humidity (%)	Max Humidity (%)	Median Humidity (%)	Hot Spot Button	Cool Spot Button
Penedo Urban Park	July 16, 2025	207	5	29.0	34.6	31.9	25.9	50.6	31.0	25	14
Quinta da Carreira Urban Park	July 23, 2025	653	5	20.9	31.3	23.7	31.0	73.6	55.8	36	86
Bosque das Fontainhas	August 06, 2025	151	1	24.7	33.9	28.7	35.3	69.1	55.4	4	0
Trajouce Urban Park	August 20, 2025	71	4	23.6	29.0	26.8	42.7	72.1	48.7	12	4
Abóboda Urban Park	August 27, 2025	177	3	20.9	32.0	25.3	46.6	69.7	59.0	5	4
Jardim Constantino	September 03, 2025	544	4	25.5	32.1	28.0	38.2	70.7	56.1	4	31
Cascais Centre	September 10, 2025	134	4	24.5	32.4	27.1	48.2	79.7	65.6	0	19

The Heat Stress Campaign generated a comprehensive hybrid dataset by combining perception surveys with TRH sensor measurements across four summer campaign events. The results validated citizen perceptions, as sensor data confirmed significant differences in temperature and humidity between parks, correlating strongly with reported comfort levels. Clear comfort and discomfort hotspots were identified: Quinta da Carreira consistently emerged as the most comfortable park, while Penedo and Bosque das Fontainhas were confirmed as high-stress areas during summer, with higher temperatures and lower perceived comfort. Importantly, the findings were taken up in policy, informing the Green Spaces and Tree Protection Regulation and shaping municipal priorities under the Cascais Climate Adaptation Plan. Specifically, the data on citizens' thermal comfort and environmental measurements helped identify which parks and urban areas are most vulnerable to heat stress, guiding decisions on tree planting, shading, and vegetation management. The perceptual data, showing areas where residents felt extreme heat, combined with the TRH sensor measurements of temperature and humidity, were particularly influential in determining priority locations for cooling interventions and green infrastructure improvements.

Beyond the data, the campaign had a noticeable impact on behaviour and raised public awareness of heat stress as a climate risk. Participants frequently reported adjusting their routines by choosing cooler parks on hot days, insights gathered through informal conversations during the sessions. These community reactions, alongside the objective measurements from TRH sensors, helped to create a fuller picture of how people experience heat in urban spaces. Municipal communication channels also played a key role, ensuring that the issue remained visible on the public agenda. The deployment of TRH sensors marked a significant step forward, enabling the campaign to combine subjective perceptions with objective environmental data, thereby providing robust evidence to guide future urban planning and adaptation measures.

Community reactions were broadly positive. Elderly citizens appreciated being actively included in climate initiatives, while youth volunteers valued the hands-on training with environmental monitoring equipment, which connected scientific learning with civic responsibility. Stakeholders recognised the campaign as a model of participatory governance, bridging citizen voices and policy action.

Several aspects of the campaign worked particularly well. The seasonal structure-maintained citizen engagement across the summer months, the integration of surveys with TRH sensors increased both credibility and relevance of the results, and public feedback loops through events and reports reinforced transparency and trust. At the same time, areas for improvement were identified. Some parks had lower levels of participation, requiring more targeted outreach, and while awareness increased, sustaining long-term behavioural change—such as consistent use of cooler parks during heatwaves—remains a challenge.

The main lessons learned highlight the added value of combining citizen science with environmental monitoring, which together generate more compelling and policy-relevant evidence than either approach alone. They also show that inclusivity requires multiple entry points, both digital and facilitated, and that youth engagement is pivotal in sustaining participation.

Overall, the Heat Stress Campaign proved effective not only in producing actionable data for municipal planning but also in strengthening public understanding of climate risks and fostering a sense of shared responsibility for adaptation.

2.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

The Heat Stress Campaign will continue to evolve as a central component of the Cascais Urban ReLeaf pilot.

Next steps include expanding the network of TRH sensors across additional parks and urban areas to ensure broader geographic coverage and improved representativeness. The findings will be further integrated into the Cascais Climate Adaptation Plan, supporting structural interventions such as increased tree planting, shading infrastructure, and the redesign of discomfort hotspots like Abóboda, Penedo and Bosque das Fontainhas. In parallel, the campaign's approach will be embedded into ongoing municipal strategies for urban greening and resilience, ensuring a long-term policy impact that extends beyond the Urban ReLeaf project lifecycle.

The campaign has already demonstrated how hybrid citizen science can inform both strategic frameworks and day-to-day planning. Moving forward, results will continue to shape local regulations on greenspace management and tree protection, guide investment priorities in cooling infrastructure and park redesign, and underpin awareness campaigns on heat stress and climate adaptation at the community level.

With its innovative approach, the Heat Stress Campaign also offers strong potential for replication in other European cities. The model can be transferred by using low-cost environmental sensors in combination with citizen perception surveys, structuring campaigns

around seasonal cycles to capture climatic variability, and establishing cross-sector partnerships among municipalities, schools, NGOs, and volunteer programmes. A key factor for replication is ensuring that citizen science outputs feed directly into policy instruments, thereby enhancing both legitimacy and impact.

At the same time, several opportunities for improvement have been identified. Inclusiveness can be broadened by specifically targeting migrant communities and citizens with limited mobility, ensuring that all voices are represented. Interactive tools and dashboards could be developed to share real-time or seasonal results with citizens, enhancing transparency and engagement. Capacity-building efforts could be strengthened by offering workshops for schools and volunteers on climate monitoring, linking data collection with education and empowerment. Finally, stronger integration of campaign outcomes with regional and national adaptation strategies would reinforce the value of Cascais as a demonstrator city.

By pursuing these actions, the Heat Stress Campaign will not only consolidate its contribution to Cascais' climate resilience but also enhance Urban ReLeaf's role as a European leader in citizen-powered environmental monitoring and inclusive urban adaptation planning.

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Appendices

Appendix A – Communication materials

COMUNICADO DE IMPRENSA

Cascais vai investir na ciência cidadã para estudar os impactos dos espaços verdes urbanos na adaptação às alterações climáticas.

O município de Cascais vai promover esta iniciativa em sete espaços verdes urbanos - Parque Urbano do Penedo, Parque Urbano da Quinta da Carreira, Parque Urbano da Abóboda, Bosque das Fontainhas, Parque Urbano de Trajouce e no Centro de Cascais, onde haverá pela primeira vez o envolvimento ativo dos cidadãos na avaliação do conforto térmico e bioclimático. Aqui, os utilizadores dos espaços vão disponibilizar informação valiosa sobre as suas experiências, cooperando para a tomada de decisões de planeamento urbano, permitindo o desenho de espaços verdes à prova de futuro.

A campanha de recolha de dados terá a duração de um ano e meio, tendo início em maio de 2024 e término em outubro de 2025, e será efetuada a partir de sensores móveis que recolhem dados de humidade e temperatura e de um questionário de satisfação ambiental, disponível em painéis informativos que estarão nas áreas de estudo. Todos os cidadãos são convidados a participar nesta iniciativa e a dar contributos para o desenho de futuros espaços naturalizados em Cascais.

Todas as informações sobre o projeto estão disponíveis no site (www.urbanreleaf.eu).

O projeto ~~Urban ReLeaf~~ cofinanciado pelo programa Horizonte Europa, pretende avaliar os impactos (custos e benefícios) dos espaços verdes urbanos e soluções baseadas na natureza para a segurança e o bem-estar da população, num contexto de alterações climáticas. O projeto é coordenado pela [IIASA](#) e conta com 15 parceiros, incluindo [6 cidades](#), tendo como objetivo cocriar soluções com os cidadãos para apoiar a adaptação às alterações climáticas, de modo a ocorrer para uma transição verde, através da criação de projetos-piloto.

Pode acompanhar o projeto nos canais das redes sociais:

LinkedIn: Urban ReLeaf

Instagram: ~~releafcities~~

X: @releafcities

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

NOME DO PROJETO	Urban ReLeaf
CONTEXTO	<p>O projeto Urban ReLeaf cofinanciado pelo programa Horizonte Europa, pretende avaliar os impactos (custos e benefícios) dos espaços verdes urbanos e soluções baseadas na natureza num contexto de alterações climáticas. Ou seja, o projeto facilitará a partilha por parte de cidadãos, de experiências de conforto térmico e bioclimático enquanto utilizam os espaços verdes, disponibilizando informação valiosa para a tomada de decisões de planeamento urbano.</p> <p>Este projeto tem como objetivos:</p>
ATIVIDADES A DESENVOLVER	<p>Durante os dias de recolha dos dados, os voluntários convidam os transeútes dos vários parques a participar na recolha de dados (preencher questionário online, descarregar aplicação e colocarem os sensores na roupa).</p> <p>No fim do percurso, os participantes recebem um brinde de participação.</p>
REQUISITOS ESPECÍFICOS	<p>Apoio nas montagens e desmontagens do evento (flag-banners); Apoiar e encaminhar os participantes para espaço para a recolha de dados (questionário, app e sensores); Divulgação do projeto.</p>
LOCAL, DATA E HORÁRIO	<p>15 de julho: horário e local a definir - formação 16 de julho: 14h30 – PU Penedo 23 de julho: 10h00 – PU Qta Carreira 6 de agosto: 14h30 - Bosque das Fontainhas 20 de agosto: 14h30 – PU Trajouce 27 de agosto: 10h00 – PU Abêdo</p>
BOLSA A ATRIBUIR	<p>3,50€/h até 5h 20€ se 6 horas ou mais. De acordo com a Normas em vigor, a entidade requisitante suporta 50% do pagamento da bolsa dos participantes, o mesmo deve ser transferido para a rubrica 02 006 2002/100 20.</p>
ALIMENTAÇÃO/ TRANSPORTES	Não incluído
Nº DE VAGAS	DATA LIMITE DA CANDIDATURA
21 (3 voluntários por parque)	1 Julho

Appendix B – Survey instruments

Questions from the survey in Portuguese completed by participants:

Contexto da visita ao local

Qual é o sítio que visita?

- Parque Urbano do Penedo
- Parque Urbano Quinta da Carreira
- Parque Urbano da Abóboda
- Bosque das Fontainhas
- Parque Urbano de Trajouce
- Centro de Cascais
- Jardim Constantino

Quais as atividades que realiza durante a sua visita a este local?

- Descanso
- Lazer
- Passear
- Convívio
- Exercício físico
- Passear o cão

Qual é a estação do ano em que está a visitar este local?

- Inverno
- Primavera
- Verão
- Outono

Com que frequência visita este local?

- Ocasionalmente
- Uma vez por semana
- Uma vez por mês
- Todos os dias

Em que período costuma visitar este local?

- Manhã
- Tarde

Qual é a importância destes fatores para a sua permanência neste local? (muito importante, importante, pouco importante, nada importante) como uma escala Likert

- Qualidade do Ar
- Nível de ruído
- Aparência visual/paisagística

Qual é a importância que dá à presença das seguintes infraestruturas? (muito importante, importante, pouco importante, nada importante) como uma escala Likert

- Bebedouros
- Bancos
- Instalações sanitárias
- Percursos
- Parques Infantis
- Mesas de piquenique

Como se sente relativamente à temperatura neste local?

- Nada confortável (muito frio ou muito calor)
- Pouco confortável (frio ou calor)
- Confortável (agradável)
- Muito confortável (sensação ótima)

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for 'Urban ReLeaf - Cascais'. The header includes the time '13:10', signal strength, 5G, and battery icons. The browser address bar shows 'partimap.eu'. The app title is 'Urban ReLeaf - Cascais'. Below the title, there is a text prompt: 'Colabore neste processo e ajude-nos a mapear os níveis de conforto climático em Cascais.' The main survey question is 'Qual é o sítio que visita?' with a dropdown menu. Below this is another question: 'Quais as atividades que realiza durante a sua visita a este local?' with a list of checkboxes: 'Descanso', 'Lazer', 'Passear', 'Convívio', 'Exercício físico', 'Passear o cão', and 'Other...'. The next question is 'Com que frequência visita este local?' with a dropdown menu. The interface also features a map on the right side and navigation buttons at the bottom.

Como se sente relativamente à humidade neste local?

- Nada confortável (muito seco ou muito húmido)
- Pouco confortável (seco ou húmido)
- Confortável (agradável)
- Muito confortável (sensação ótima)

Como se sente relativamente à radiação solar neste local?

- Nada confortável (muito escuro ou muito claro)
- Pouco confortável (escuro ou claro)
- Confortável (agradável)
- Muito confortável (sensação ótima)

Como se sente relativamente ao vento neste local?

- Nada confortável (sem vento ou muito vento)
- Pouco confortável (ventoso)
- Confortável (agradável)
- Muito confortável (se sente ótimo)

Satisfação geral

Como você se sente em visitar este lugar?

- Nada confortável
- Pouco confortável
- Confortável
- Muito confortável

Comentários e sugestões para melhoria do espaço e serviços prestados.

Caracterização geral do inquirido

Idade

- Até 15 anos
- 16 - 25anos
- 26 - 35anos
- 36 - 45anos
- 46 - 55anos
- 56 - 65anos
- Mais de 65 anos

Género

- Feminino
- Masculino
- Outro

Residência

- Concelho de Cascais
- Fora do país
- Outro Município

Nível de escolaridade

- Ensino Básico
- Ensino Secundário
- Ensino Superior

Questions from the survey in English completed by participants:

Context of the Site Visit

Which place do you visit?

- Parque Urbano do Penedo
- Parque Urbano Quinta da Carreira
- Parque Urbano Abóboda
- Bosque Fontainhas
- Parque Urbano Trajouce
- Centro de Cascais
- Jardim Constantino

What activities do you carry out during your visit to this location?

- Resting
- Leisure
- Walking
- Socialising
- Physical exercise
- Pleasant Landscape
- Walking the Dog

What season are you visiting this place?

- Winter
- Spring
- Summer
- Autumn

How often do you visit this place?

- Occasionally
- Once a week
- Once a month
- Every day

What is your preferred time to visit this place?

- Morning
- Afternoon

How significant are these factors for your stay here? (very important, important, not so important, not important) like a Likert Scale

Air Quality

Noise Level

Visual/landscape appearance

How significant is the presence of the following infrastructures? (very important, important, not so important, not important) like a Likert Scale

Drinking fountains

Benches

Sanitary facilities

Paths

Playgrounds

Picnic tables

How do you feel about the temperature here?

- Not Comfortable (Too Cold or Too Hot)
- Not Very Comfortable (Cold or Hot)
- Comfortable (Pleasant)
- Very Comfortable (Feels Great)

How do you feel about the humidity in this place?

13:10 5G

partimap.eu

Urban ReLeaf - Cascais

Please take part in this survey and help us map the climate comfort levels in Cascais.

* Which place are you visiting?

What activities do you carry out during your visit?

Resting

Leisure

Walking

Socialising

Physical exercise

Enjoying the landscape

Walking a dog

Other...

How often do you visit this place?

- Not Comfortable (Very Dry or Very Humid)
- Not Very Comfortable (Dry or Damp)
- Comfortable (Pleasant)
- Very Comfortable (Feels Great)

How do you feel about solar radiation in this place?

- Not Comfortable (Too Dark or Too Light)
- Not Very Comfortable (Dark or Light)
- Comfortable (Pleasant)
- Very Comfortable (Feels Great)

How do you feel about the wind in this place?

- Not Comfortable (No Wind or Lots of Wind)
- Not Very Comfortable (Windy)
- Comfortable (Pleasant)
- Very Comfortable (Feels Great)

General satisfaction

How do you feel about visiting this place?

- Not Comfortable
- Not Very Comfortable
- Comfortable
- Very Comfortable

Comments and suggestions for improving the space and services provided.

General characterisation of the respondent

Age

Gender

Residence

Educational Level

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Signage in urban greenspaces that are being studied in the project, where participants can access the survey via the QR code on the sign.

 Urban ReLeaf

Um parque urbano para o futuro

Sabia que os espaços verdes tornam Cascais mais resiliente às alterações climáticas?

Cascais é um município preparado para o futuro e comprometido com a ação climática!

Os espaços verdes urbanos são refúgios de bem-estar e conforto face a fenómenos climáticos extremos.

Partilhe a sua experiência, avaliando o seu conforto térmico e bioclimático neste local e contribua para o desenho de futuros espaços verdes em Cascais.

Aceda ao questionário através do QRCode.

Faça parte deste processo e ajude-nos a mapear os níveis de conforto climático em Cascais!

Para saber mais sobre o projeto, visite o site www.urbanreleaf.eu
@releafcities #releafcities

A future-proof urban park

Do you know green spaces help Cascais to be more resilient to climate change?

Cascais is a future-ready municipality committed to climate action!

Urban green spaces are havens of well-being and comfort in the face of extreme weather events.

Share your experience by evaluating your thermal and bioclimatic comfort and contribute to the design of future green spaces in Cascais.

Use the QRCode to access the survey.

Be a part of this process and help us map the levels of climate comfort in Cascais!

To find out more about the project, visit the website www.urbanreleaf.eu
@releafcities #releafcities

Appendix C – Campaign datasets summary

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Summer Results – preliminary findings

KPIs status

- **No. of citizens** engaged – 1068 answers
 - 287 spring campaign
 - 552 summer campaign
 - 229 autumn campaign
- **Share of women** and participants from vulnerable/marginalised groups
 - 60% are women
 - 18% up to 24 years
 - 13% over 65 years
 - 5,6% basic education
- **No. of policies** that will make direct use of project data
 - Green Spaces and Tree Protection Regulation
 - Good Practice Manual “Renatura”

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